

Supercritical carbon dioxide extraction of Portuguese rice bran oil

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GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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Rice bran is a by-product (about 8 % of rice paddy) originated from the rice grinding process in which the outer layers of the rice kernel are removed. Rice bran consists of 11–15% proteins, 34–62% carbohydrates, 7–11% crude fibers, 7–10% ashes and 15–20% lipids, which are a by-product of the rice-refining process [1]. Supplement of rice bran in various foods provides to the progress of value-added foods or functional foods that now are of increasing benefit to the society. Rice bran has been profitably enhanced in bread, cakes, noodles, pasta, and ice creams without any negative effect on their functional and textural properties [2].

Supercritical carbon dioxide extraction, scCO₂, of oils from samples of rice bran, 16 g, was carried out in the flow apparatus, from Applied Separations, (Spe-ed™ SFE) at

temperatures from 313.2 to 333.2 K, pressures up to 40.0 MPa and CO₂ flow rates from 0.12 kg/h to 0.32 kg/h [3].

Analysis of the extracted oils by GC-FID, revealed the composition of the oils being oleic acid 52%, the main compound, followed linoleic acid 29%, palmitic acid 15%, and stearic acid 1.6%.

To estimate the susceptibility to oxidation of oils, the allylic position equivalent (APE) and bis-allylic position equivalent (BAPE) [4] indexes and oxidizability (OX) [5] were calculated using the content of each fatty acid. Moreover, there was a slight difference in extraction kinetics in the relative percentage of the total unsaturation index (UI).

A discussion of the modelling of our data on supercritical fluid extraction of rice bran oil was carried out. The results obtained at different extraction conditions using only one [6] or two [7] adjustable parameter, provided a fairly good agreement between the model curves and the experimental data, which evidence the capability of these models.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

J.P. Coelho acknowledge the funding received from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement N° 778168 and are thankful for the financial support from Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, Portugal, under projects UID/QUI/00100/2019.

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